

Optimized Tile Quality Selection in Multi-user 360° Video Streaming

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ABSTRACT 360° videos and virtual reality (VR) are among the defining applications for a new era of immersive multimedia technologies. However, streaming high-quality 360° videos constitutes a challenge for service providers and network operators, especially in multi-user scenarios. The massive data rates and the unique features of omnidirectional videos necessitate the development of novel streaming techniques. In this paper, we propose an optimized multi-user tiled 360° video streaming framework. Specifically, we formulate the problem of tile quality selection in multi-user bandwidth-constrained communications and propose an algorithm that assigns the quality levels of transmitted tiles. The proposed framework is designed to maximize the perceived quality within the users' viewports by considering 360° video quality assessment (360° VQA) metrics and tile viewing percentages. To simulate our solution in practical settings, we employ a long short-term memory (LSTM) model to perform viewport prediction and make the assessment based on real-life viewing data. Simulation results of our proposed framework show significant improvement in the delivered viewports' quality and robustness against increasing the number of users.

INDEX TERMS video streaming, video quality assessment (VQA), virtual reality (VR), 360° videos

I. INTRODUCTION

Immersive technologies have revolutionized multimedia applications, altering how we interact with digital content. Virtual reality (VR) and 360° videos provide users with an interactive experience, allowing them to explore spherical scenes by simply moving their heads in the desired direction. In typical VR setups, users utilize head-mounted display (HMD) devices to immerse themselves in virtual environments. Commercial HMD devices such as HTC VIVE Pro 2 [1] and Meta Quest 3 [2] are now available with various specifications, catering to diverse user needs and preferences. The rapid development of VR technologies encouraged the adoption of such applications in a variety of domains, including education [3], healthcare [4], sports coverage [5], and cultural venues [6].

Over the past decades, enormous efforts have been dedicated to enhancing video streaming efficiency. Nowadays, platforms such as Netflix and YouTube provide high-quality videos to billions of users worldwide. Nonetheless, employing conventional streaming strategies for delivering omnidirectional videos is suboptimal and oftentimes impractical. Despite the excitement brought by immersive video applications, delivering such types of content poses additional challenges for service providers and network operators [7]. Compared to conventional 2D videos, 360° videos have significantly higher bitrate demands and tighter

latency requirements [8]. The spherical nature of omnidirectional videos translates to huge video sizes, creating a burden on communication networks. Quality of experience (QoE) studies also demonstrate the importance of low-latency delivery for ensuring a convenient user experience.

In recent years, various innovative strategies have been developed to tackle these challenges, leveraging the unique characteristics of 360° videos. In tile-based streaming [9], the 360° video is first projected into a two-dimensional shape, e.g., equirectangular projection (ERP), and then is divided into smaller rectangular tiles. The resulting tiles are hence encoded and transmitted independently from each other. Tiled streaming results in significant bandwidth savings. At any specific time, a VR user watches part of the overall spherical scene. This area of the video is referred to as the user's viewport or field of view (FoV). Tile-based delivery capitalizes on this fact by prioritizing tiles relevant to the user's viewport by assigning them higher qualities. This in turn, enhances the displayed content while respecting bandwidth constraints. Consequently, the tile quality selection arises as an optimization problem to be solved, depending on the transmission objectives and communication setup. In multi-user environments, viewport overlaps influence tile quality selection decisions [10], [11].

For tile-based streaming to be employed efficiently, the user's viewing direction must be known to the system.

However, since VR users can change their viewing direction at any time, future viewports cannot be determined in advance and only previous tracking traces can be obtained from HMD devices. Given this, and to provide a proactive transmission that could meet the stringent latency requirements of 360° videos, viewport prediction has been investigated to forecast future viewports [12], [13], [14].

Another distinction from conventional videos is related to video quality assessment (VQA) methods. Established VQA metrics such as peak signal-to-noise ratio (PSNR) and the structural similarity (SSIM) index [15] have been utilized to optimize the delivered quality in video streaming frameworks. Nonetheless, 360° VQA methods such as spherical PSNR (S-PSNR) [16] and weighted-to-spherical PSNR (WS-PSNR) [17] have been recently developed to account for the unique features of omnidirectional videos. Additionally, more accurate assessments can be obtained by considering the user's FoV, rather than the whole 360° video frame. Although existing research considered different aspects of 360° video streaming, 360° VQA metrics have been rarely considered as the optimization objective.

In this paper, a proactive multi-user tiled 360° video streaming framework is proposed to maximize the users' viewport quality in bandwidth-constrained scenarios. The main contributions of this work are summarized as follows:

- We formulate the tile quality selection problem in multi-user 360° video streaming as a multiple-choice knapsack problem (MCKP) to maximize a viewport-based 360° VQA metric in bandwidth-constrained scenarios. This formulation aims to provide users with a satisfactory viewing experience by considering the unique features of 360° videos and users' viewing behavior.
- We propose a greedy algorithm that maximizes the WS-PSNR within the users' viewports by assigning the optimal quality level to each tile. Our method prioritizes tiles with the highest influence on the overall quality perceived by the system users. This strategy ensures an adequate viewing experience for the users, even in limited-bandwidth scenarios.
- We employ a long short-term memory (LSTM) network for tile-level prediction and integrate it within the 360° video transmission framework to evaluate our method in practical proactive scenarios. We show that our methodology is resilient to viewport prediction errors and is suitable for proactive multi-user transmission.

Section II of this paper presents an overview of related work. In Section III, we analyze the viewing behavior of VR users watching 360° videos and discuss viewport-based 360° VQA to motivate our work. The adopted system model, the formulation of the tile quality selection problem, and the proposed method are introduced in Section IV. Section V details the experimental setup and presents the performance evaluation. Finally, we conclude our paper in Section VI.

II. RELATED WORK

Tiling is a popular strategy applied in 360° video streaming that provides a practical solution for effective and optimized delivery [18]. In tile-based streaming, the omnidirectional video is projected into a 2D rectangular shape using the ERP scheme. It is then divided into smaller rectangular tiles, where the tiling configuration is a trade-off between encoding efficiency and streaming flexibility [19]. Each tile is encoded and transmitted independently from others, to be combined again at the user's end. Since the VR user watches only part of the spherical video, only a subset of the overall tiles should be transmitted at high quality. Our work proposes a new approach to viewport tiles optimization based on 360° VQA metrics. We discuss in this section works that are relevant to our contribution, focusing mainly on optimized tiled 360° video streaming and multiple-user streaming optimization.

Efficient tiled 360° video streaming requires careful decisions on which tiles should be sent and at what quality level. Many efforts have been dedicated to optimizing tile-based 360° video transmission. In [20], a tile bitrate selection algorithm in limited-bandwidth communications was introduced. In this work, the average bitrate in the user's viewport is adopted as one of the QoE optimization factors. The authors in [21] proposed an adaptive streaming method that assigns different bitrates to different tiles, depending on the user's viewing behavior and network conditions. They adopted a reward function based on the quality of user experience, considering the viewing video bitrate. Although increasing the bitrate of viewed tiles, as in [20] and [21], generally increases the perceived quality, the relationship between the two is not strong. Therefore, our work targets the delivered 360° VQA metrics, directly enhancing the users' perceived quality. Moreover, we consider tile viewing percentages to prioritize more influential tiles. Prioritizing viewport central tiles over partially viewed edge tiles is more aligned with the overall quality experienced by the end users.

In the presence of multiple users, overlaps among users' viewports become a deciding factor in streaming optimization. The authors in [22] investigated different multicasting strategies for multi-quality tiled 360° video streaming. In addition to natural multicast opportunities, they considered multicasting with relative smoothness and transcoding-enabled scenarios. The arising multicasting opportunities in each of the adopted scenarios have been exploited to minimize the energy consumption in the system. In [23], a multi-user VR delivery system was presented. The authors introduced a tile bit-assignment algorithm for efficient optimization of the resources within bandwidth constraints. The proposed delivery scheme avoids redundant transmissions and dynamically switches between unicast and multicast modes based on estimated viewing tiles and user view similarities. A scalable multicasting framework for multiuser 360° video streaming was introduced in [24]. In this work, tiles are encoded at multiple quality layers. Efficient resource utilization is performed by transmitting enhancement layers of viewport tiles and by exploiting cross-user similarity for multicasting tiles that are watched by multiple users.

Figure 1. Analysis of users' viewing characteristics while watching 360° videos. (a) Snapshots from four videos. (b) Heatmaps of the viewport center points obtained from 20 users. (c) Implications of increasing the number of users on tile viewing (correspond to an 8x8 tiling grid).

III. 360° VIDEO VIEWING CHARACTERISTICS

In this section, we perform an analysis to showcase the viewing patterns and characteristics that arise when humans watch omnidirectional videos. We illustrate humans' tendency to focus on specific engaging areas within different videos. We also inspect correlations among users' viewports and examine their implications on multi-user tiled 360° video streaming setups. Next, we provide a discussion on 360° VQA methods and viewport quality, motivating our choice to work with viewport-based 360° VQA.

A. Viewing behavior analysis

A key enabling characteristic for efficient 360° video streaming arises from the viewing habits of VR users. Analyzing humans' behavior while watching 360° videos uncovers interesting patterns among their viewing trajectories. Typically, people's attention tends to be guided to certain parts of the video scenes. These parts can be characterized by their engaging events or by distinct moving objects. For example, in a 360° video showing a football game, most users focus on the part of the video that contains the ball. It is also common for VR users to view content along the "equator", i.e., the horizontal central axis. In general, horizontal explorations of 360° videos are more dominant than vertical explorations because in practice most videos do not contain engaging content at the top and bottom areas of the video frame (e.g., it is very common for the top part to contain an empty sky and the bottom to be just the ground). Moreover, it is more convenient for the users to keep their heads at normal levels. These observations result in high correlations among users' FoVs, leaving substantial parts of the videos unwatched. Nonetheless, correlations between users' viewports can vary

depending on the specific video content and the user watching it. Such observations are seen in the literature across different 360° video viewing datasets and different experimental setups [25], [26], [27]. Moreover, omnidirectional scene navigation usually occurs at a slow steady pace, which facilitates accurate viewport prediction within reasonable periods (e.g., 1-2 seconds) [28], [29]. Therefore, understanding the viewing patterns is crucial for both 360° video transmission and viewport prediction.

In the context of multi-user tiled 360° videos, overlapping viewports translate into overlapping in viewed tiles. To investigate the implications of increasing the number of VR users on viewed tiles, we analyze the users' watching traces in the ODV-VQA [30] dataset. Figure 1 illustrates the viewing behavior of users while watching videos that belong to different categories. Figure 1b shows a heatmap based on the viewing center points of twenty different users watching each of the four presented videos. As depicted in this figure, different viewing patterns arise depending on the content of the video. In the first video, users mostly focused their attention on the biker who happens to be at the center of the video. A more scattered pattern appears in the HatchWaterfall video, as users navigate various parts of the scenery without focusing on a specific object. The corresponding viewed tiles are then examined for different numbers of users. Figure 1c presents the watched tiles percentage (in black) and the average number of users per tile (in blue) as the concurrent number of users increases from one to ten. To produce this figure, an 8x8 tiling grid is adopted and the results are obtained over 1s segments. Naturally, an increase in the number of users results in a larger number of the overall watched tiles. However, since the users tend to view similar or adjacent parts of the videos, the increase is not directly linear. For instance,

even with ten users concurrently watching the BikingInSaalbach video, only ~55% of the overall tiles are required. The number of users per tile is also shown (in blue) and indicates that most tiles are being watched by multiple users when the total number of users in the system increases. The results introduced in Figure 1 affirm the possible benefits of tiled streaming. Even with the presence of multiple users, many tiles are still not watched by any of the users. Therefore, a substantial bandwidth reduction can be achieved by transmitting only the relevant tiles and avoiding the transmission of unnecessary tiles. It should be noted that although we present the analysis of only four videos, these patterns can be observed in all real-life omnidirectional video viewing scenarios where the specific video content plays a role in the resulting viewport correlations and viewing patterns. In Figure 2, we present the distribution of yaw and pitch angles belonging to a total of 108 360° videos where each video is watched by 20-40 users. The corresponding fitted Gaussian mixture model (GMM) for each case is also plotted. It can be observed that the majority of viewing traces, representing the center of viewports, are concentrated around the center of video frames. Moreover, the exploration along the horizontal axis is more dominant than the vertical one. The videos in this analysis belong to the ODV-VQA dataset and the VR-HM48 dataset [31]. These two datasets include the viewing traces of participants watching different 360° videos that belong to various categories. Yet, they both exhibit very close viewing distributions, which indicates that this behavior is universal across typical real-life omnidirectional videos. These observations also align with similar works in the literature [25], [26], [27]. Therefore, leveraging users' viewing behavior through the associated tile viewing similarities creates vital opportunities for optimizing the delivery of 360° videos that can be highly beneficial for most real-life omnidirectional video content.

Within the user's viewport, central tiles are usually watched fully, and their quality highly affects the user's experience, whereas tiles at the edge of the viewport might be less important as only a small portion of these tiles might actually end up being watched, depending on the user's exact viewing direction. Therefore, assigning higher quality for tiles with higher viewing percentages, i.e., the number of viewed pixels within tiles, is an efficient approach under limited bandwidth conditions. Given the high correlation among users' viewports, central "important" tiles are usually the same for all or most users. Thus, leveraging the combined tiles watching percentages becomes even more crucial as it also affects the collective viewing experience. Figure 3 illustrates the tile viewing percentages for three users watching the same 360° video segment and the corresponding combined viewing ratios. As these users have similar viewing directions, assigning higher qualities for common tiles and fully-watched tiles is naturally preferable over edge tiles watched by only one (or few) users. Prioritizing tiles that are watched fully by many users over tiles watched partially by less users would enhance the quality of most relevant parts of the video while still

Figure 2. Distribution of yaw and pitch angles.

Figure 3. Combined tiles' viewing percentages for a common video segment.

delivering acceptable quality for less critical regions, depending on the available bandwidth. Therefore, as we explain in the next section, we quantify the viewing percentage values and opt for utilizing them in the tile quality assignment optimization.

B. Viewport quality in tile-based 360° video streaming

Video compression is an integral process in video transmission that allows for efficient storage and streaming at manageable sizes. Nonetheless, this comes at the cost of video quality degradation, depending on the video codec and the used encoding parameters. In practice, a balance between the video bitrate and the resulting quality is made. Since the perceived quality is subject to the user experience, it cannot be

known in advance. In consequence, full-reference video quality assessment methods have been developed to provide objective numerical metrics by comparing encoded videos to their corresponding undistorted reference videos. The PSNR is an established method that calculates a quality metric by comparing the reference and encoded sequences based on pixel-level values. Many VQA methods have been designed, employing various visual features of conventional 2D videos [32]. Nonetheless, these methods often fall short when applied to 360° videos. Although omnidirectional videos can be projected into 2D shapes, they are intended to be watched in their spherical format. This introduces several complexities that necessitate specialized considerations for accurate quality assessment. To address these issues, 360° VQA metrics have been introduced to account for projection implications and provide more precise evaluations that specifically target the spherical nature of 360° videos.

Since the relationship between the spherical watching space and the 2D encoding space is nonlinear, different variations of PSNR-based 360° VQA metrics have been developed to account for mapping nonuniformities that occur when projecting spherical videos into 2D shapes and vice versa. The S-PSNR metric compares the pixel values of the reference and original frames depending on their corresponding uniformly sampled spheres, which allows for the evaluation of videos with different panoramic projections. In WS-PSNR, pixel value differences are calculated similarly to PSNR and weighted depending on their positions within the scene. The Crasters parabolic projection (CPP-PSNR) [33] transforms the video frames into the Crasters parabolic projection format before calculating the PSNR values. Hence, it can be used even if the reference and impaired frames have different projection formats and resolutions.

Previous works in the context of conventional 2D video streaming emphasized the importance of considering classical VQA metrics such as PSNR and SSIM in the optimization process due to their direct correlation to the video quality [34], [35], [36]. With the development of robust 360° VQA metrics which target 360° videos, we take the initiative to leverage these metrics for 360° video streaming setups. Many works in tile-based 360° video streaming optimization can be found in the literature but, to the best of our knowledge, 360° VQA metrics have not been considered in tile-based 360° video streaming as an optimization target. Previous works that focus on delivering high-quality 360° video content take either bitrate or quality level as representative values for delivered quality [20], [21], [37], [38], [39]. However, bitrates and quality levels are not the best values to reflect perceived quality. Therefore, we propose in this work to maximize the 360° VQA metrics of delivered viewports, as 360° VQA metrics are primarily designed to reflect the quality of 360° as experienced by humans. In tiled 360° video streaming, the quality level of different tiles contributes differently to the overall perceived quality depending on the tiles' content and their location with respect to the user's FoV. Ideally, tiles outside the users' viewport do not need to be transmitted. In

some settings, however, it is advisable to send these tiles at low quality to anticipate possible errors in viewport prediction while maintaining reasonable bandwidth usage. Therefore, the major bandwidth utilization is given to increase the quality of viewport tiles. In bandwidth-constrained scenarios, optimized transmission extends to assigning quality levels to individual viewport tiles. Rather than sending viewport tiles at a uniform quality level, a more intelligent approach should consider encoding bitrates and the contribution of each tile to the overall perceived quality. In addition to associated 360° VQA metrics, the contribution of each tile to the overall perceived quality also depends on the viewed percentage of this tile, as discussed in the previous subsection.

In this work, we formulate the tile quality assignment problem in multi-user bandwidth-constrained streaming with the intent of maximizing the viewport's WS-PSNR (VWS-PSNR). As we explain in the next section, we tailor the calculation of the WS-PSNR metric to consider relevant tiles of the video and formulate the optimization problem accordingly. We specifically opted to utilize WS-PSNR due to its simplicity compared to other methods, while having the ability to provide reliable measurements [40]. Nonetheless, other 360° VQA metrics can also be adapted to carry out the optimization similarly.

IV. METHODOLOGY

In this section, we provide system modeling along with the optimization problem formulation. We also formulate the tile viewing prediction problem. Then, we introduce our proposed method to tackle the resulting optimization problem. The notations used in our approach are described in Table 1.

TABLE 1. Mathematical notations.

Symbol	Meaning
U	Number of concurrent users watching the 360° video
M	Number of horizontal tiles
N	Number of vertical tiles
T	Set of $M \times N$ total tiles
P_H	Video horizontal pixel resolution
P_V	Video vertical pixel resolution
K	Number of segment frames
θ_k^u	Yaw angle of user u viewing direction at timeframe k
ϕ_k^u	Pitch angle of user u viewing direction at timeframe k
Q	Number of available encoding levels
BW	System bandwidth
$b_{m,n,q}$	Bitrate of tile $T_{m,n}$ at encoding quality q
$\alpha_{m,n}^u$	Viewing ratio of tile $T_{m,n}$ by user u
$\hat{\alpha}_{m,n}^u$	Predicted viewing ratio of tile $T_{m,n}$ by user u
$f_w(\cdot)$	Tile viewing prediction model with trainable parameters W
$\mathcal{L}_W(\cdot)$	Loss function of the prediction model

Figure 4. Architecture of the multi-user 360° video transmission system.

A. System model

In our system model, a group of U users watch a 360° video transmitted to them over a common channel. Figure 4 shows an overview of the adopted system architecture. The video is available on an edge server in ERP format and is divided into $M \times N$ tiles $T = \{T_{1,1}, \dots, T_{m,n}, \dots, T_{M,N}\}$. The video has a resolution of $P_H \times P_V$. Thus, each tile is comprised of $\frac{P_H}{M} \times \frac{P_V}{N}$ pixels. As videos are typically transmitted as independent temporal segments, we deal with segments as separate videos, each consisting of K temporal frames. At time instance k , the FoV of user u is determined by his/her viewing direction, which is given as a pair of yaw θ_k^u and pitch angles φ_k^u within the $360^\circ \times 180^\circ$ scene. This translates as a subset of tiles being watched by that user at time instance k , which we denote as $T_k^u \in T$. Nonetheless, some of these tiles may only lie partially within the user's viewport (i.e., tiles at the viewport edges). Therefore, we use $a_{k,m,n}^u$ to quantify the viewing percentage of tile m, n by user u at time instance k . This value is therefore calculated on a pixel-by-pixel basis as:

$$a_{k,m,n}^u = \frac{M \cdot N}{P_H \cdot P_V} \sum_{i=1}^{P_H/M} \sum_{j=1}^{P_V/N} \psi_{k,m,n}^u(i, j) \quad (1)$$

$\psi_{k,m,n}^u(i, j)$ is set to 1 when pixel i, j in tile m, n is within the viewport of user u at time instance k , and is set to 0 otherwise. For the overall transmission system, the watching percentage of each tile $a_{m,n}$ is then calculated by averaging the values obtained from (1) over K frames and U users. Figure 3 provides a visual representation of the $a_{m,n}^u$ values obtained from three different users watching the same video segment. It also illustrates their resulting combined $a_{m,n}$ values. Each tile is available on the server at Q encoding levels, where $T_{m,n,q}$ represents tile $T_{m,n}$ at encoding quality q . Each encoding representation $T_{m,n,q}$ is hence associated

with a bitrate $b_{m,n,q}$. Higher q levels correspond to better qualities (e.g., encoded using lower quantization parameters (QPs)) with higher bitrate demands. The selection of high-quality levels is thus limited by the system bandwidth BW .

B. Optimization Problem formulation

From the users' perspective, it is critical to assign high-quality levels to tiles that contribute the most to enhancing the quality of their viewports' content. We therefore focus on maximizing the viewport WS-PSNR (VWS-PSNR), in which we modify the WS-PSNR metric calculations to only consider pixels within the users' viewports. The VWS-PSNR value for user u is therefore calculated in dB as follows:

$$VWS_PSNR^u = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K 10 \cdot \log_{10} \frac{MAX_I^2}{VWMSE_k^u} \quad (2)$$

$$VWMSE_k^u = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{P_H} \sum_{j=1}^{P_V} \psi_k^u(i, j) \cdot (y(i, j) - y'(i, j))^2 \cdot w(i, j)}{\sum_{i=1}^{P_H} \sum_{j=1}^{P_V} \psi_k^u(i, j) \cdot w(i, j)} \quad (3)$$

$$w(i, j) = \cos \frac{(j + 0.5 - \frac{P_H}{2})\pi}{P_H} \quad (4)$$

MAX_I denotes the maximum possible intensity level of the video frame, which typically has the value 255. $\psi_k^u(i, j)$ is defined in a similar manner to $\psi_{k,m,n}^u(i, j)$, used previously in (1), with the exception that the pixel position is with respect to the whole frame rather than a specific tile.

Calculating the exact viewport quality from pixel-level values can be time-consuming. Therefore, we define the value $G_{m,n,q}^u$ to represent the contribution of tile $T_{m,n}$, when selected at quality level q , to the viewport quality of user u .

$$G_{m,n,q}^u = a_{m,n}^u \cdot WS_PSNR_{m,n,q}^u \quad (5)$$

$WS_PSNR_{m,n,q}^u$ is calculated in a similar manner to (2)-(4), but with only including the pixels within tile $T_{m,n}$ when quality level q is selected for that tile. This way, the values $G_{m,n,q}^u$ can be calculated in advance, and only tile-level

calculations are required for the tile quality selection.

We formulate a tile quality selection optimization problem to maximize the collective viewports' quality as follows:

$$\max_x \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{q=1}^Q G_{m,n,q} \cdot x_{m,n,q} \quad (6)$$

s.t.

$$\sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{q=1}^Q b_{m,n,q} \cdot x_{m,n,q} \leq BW$$

$$\sum_{q=1}^Q x_{m,n,q} = 1, x_{m,n,q} \in \{0,1\}$$

$G_{m,n,q}$ is obtained by averaging the $G_{m,n,q}^u$ values across all U users. The symbol $x_{m,n,q}$ indicates whether tile $T_{m,n}$ is selected at quality level q . Thus, the two conditions ensure the selection of one quality level for each tile, while respecting the available system bandwidth. In the formulated problem, the bandwidth is allocated on a tile-level basis, where the same tile version is multicasted to all users [41].

The maximization problem in (6) matches the descriptions of the multiple-choice knapsack problem (MCKP), which is known to be an np-hard problem. Therefore, we implement a greedy algorithm for solving it, which we describe in subsection IV-D.

C. Tile-watching prediction problem

The problem formulated in the previous subsection assumes perfect knowledge of the users' viewports. In practice, however, the future viewing directions cannot be known to the system in advance. Therefore, we employ tile-watching prediction to forecast the tile-viewing percentages for a user over the upcoming video segment. In other words, the model should return a matrix of $M \times N$ values ranging from 0 to 1.

We refer to this matrix (in bold) as $\hat{\mathbf{a}}^u$, where its elements are the predicted values for $a_{m,n}^u$, used in (5). We utilize the viewing directions within the last L timestamps to perform the forecasting. To comply with the spherical nature of 360° videos, we use the trigonometric values (sine and cosine) for the pitch and yaw angles as inputs. The use of trigonometric values is particularly beneficial for cases near the edges of the ERP video representation. We assign the symbol \mathbf{P}^u to represent the input. \mathbf{P}^u contains L elements of previous directions, where each element p_{-l}^u is given using four values $p_{-l}^u = \{\cos(\theta_{-l}^u), \sin(\theta_{-l}^u), \cos(2 \cdot \varphi_{-l}^u), \sin(2 \cdot \varphi_{-l}^u)\}$. A model $f_W(\cdot)$ with trainable weights W should thus be trained to capture the dependency between historical traces and future tile viewing. The training is performed to minimize a loss function $\mathcal{L}_W(\cdot)$. Therefore, the prediction results are obtained by:

$$\hat{\mathbf{a}}^u = f_W(\mathbf{P}^u) \quad (7)$$

where $W = \underset{W}{\operatorname{argmax}}(\mathcal{L}_W)$

Figure 5 presents the tile prediction framework with a visual illustration of the model input and expected output. In this work, we opt for using LSTM as our prediction model. More

details on the model training and prediction results are provided in the next section.

D. Proposed method

The problem defined in section IV-B is a MCKP that is known to be an np-hard problem. To tackle this problem, we implement a greedy algorithm that assigns the quality levels for the 360° video tiles. We also combine it with a tile weight prediction model to implement a comprehensive practical framework. The proposed algorithm starts by assigning the lowest quality level to all tiles and starts increasing the quality levels of tiles that lead to the highest gain in the users' perceived quality. Specifically, by capitalizing on the tile-watching percentages and their contribution to the collective VWS-PSNR.

Our algorithm also incorporates the corresponding bitrate increases into the decision-making and keeps opportunistically improving the quality of the most important tiles until the available bandwidth is fully utilized, or until all viewport tiles are at the highest quality. This opportunistic approach effectively prioritizes tiles that are watched by multiple users, especially those lying entirely within their viewports. Edge tiles and tiles viewed by fewer users, however, are given less priority and their quality is only improved when the bandwidth resources allow. Thus, the system resources are utilized efficiently to improve the end-users viewing experience. This should be especially evident in scarce bandwidth scenarios. Moreover, the algorithm is designed to be scalable and robust to high numbers of concurrent users. Algorithm 1 provides a pseudocode of our approach.

An LSTM model is employed to predict tile-watching percentages from historical viewing data and then the greedy method selects the tiles' quality levels accordingly. We opted for using LSTM networks for the tile viewing prediction due to their efficiency in time series forecasting. LSTM models have been previously utilized for viewport prediction tasks and have provided accurate estimations [42], [43]. Nonetheless, other prediction models can be incorporated instead. Our LSTM model predicts user tile-watching percentages based on historical viewing traces. Trigonometric values (sine and cosine) of previous viewing directions, as pairs of yaw and pitch angles, are fed into the model to obtain forecasted tile weights for the next video segment. The model architecture consists of two hidden layers with ReLU activation function and an output layer with a sigmoid activation function to produce prediction values in the range 0-1. The mean squared error (MSE) is adopted as the loss function in the training process:

$$\mathcal{L}_W = \frac{1}{S \cdot M \cdot N} \sum_{s=1}^S \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{m=1}^M (a_{m,n}^u - \hat{a}_{m,n}^u)^2 \quad (8)$$

Where S is the number of training observation samples belonging to different users and videos. The training process and prediction results are discussed in the next section.

Figure 5. Illustration of tiles viewing percentage prediction.

Algorithm 1 Multi-user Tile Quality Selection Greedy Algorithm

- 1: **Input:** Available bandwidth BW , Users' viewing vectors P_u for each $u \in U$, The set of tiles at a range of quality levels $T_{m,n,q}$ for each $m, n, q \in M, N, Q$
- 2: **Output:** An $M \times N$ list of selected tile quality levels *selected_tiles*
- 3: $remaining_bw \leftarrow BW$
- 4: Calculate $WS_PSNR_{m,n,q}^u \quad \forall u, m, n, q \in U, M, N, Q$
- 5: $\hat{a}^u \leftarrow LSTM(P_u) \quad \forall u \in U$
- 6: Calculate $G_{m,n,q}^u$ using eq. (5) $\forall u, m, n, q \in U, M, N, Q$
- 7: $G_{m,n,q} \leftarrow \frac{1}{U} \sum_{u=1}^U G_{m,n,q}^u \quad \forall m, n, q \in M, N, Q$
- 8: Set all tiles to lowest quality:
- 9: $selected_tiles_{m,n} \leftarrow 1 \quad \forall m, n \in M, N$
- 10: $remaining_bw \leftarrow remaining_bw - \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{n=1}^N b_{m,n,1}$
- 11: Sort tiles in descending order according to $\frac{diff(G_{m,n})}{diff(b_{m,n})}$, resulting from increasing the quality level of each tile $T_{m,n}$
- 12: **while** $min(diff(b_{m,n})) \leq remaining_bw$ **do**
- 13: Increase quality level of tile $T_{m,n}$ with maximum $\frac{diff(G_{m,n})}{diff(b_{m,n})}$ and $diff(b_{m,n}) \leq remaining_bw$ by 1
- 14: $remaining_bw \leftarrow remaining_bw - diff(b_{m,n})$
- 15: **end while**

V. EXPERIMENTS

In this section, we describe the experimental setup and simulation details. First, we introduce the 360° video dataset used in this work and outline the steps carried out to prepare the dataset for multi-quality tiled streaming. Then we present the simulation results in different scenarios.

A. Dataset preparation

We use the ODV-VQA dataset [30] for testing and evaluating our algorithm. The ODV-VQA dataset contains 60 omnidirectional videos available in YUV format. The video sequences have resolutions that range from 4K (3840 × 1920 pixels) to 8K (7680 × 3840 pixels), with temporal framerates in the range of 24-30 fps. The videos belong to a variety of categories and are in ERP format. The dataset also provides head movement (HM) and eye movement (EM) traces collected from 221 participants who watched the videos using an HTC Vive HMD. Each video has valid tracing data from at least 20 users. In this work, we use the

pitch and yaw angles of the HM data for constructing the users' viewports.

To prepare the video sequences for tiled 360° video streaming, we used FFmpeg [44] for the segmentation and tiling of the videos. Each video is hence divided into temporal segments of one-second length. We deal with each segment as a separate video. We then divide each segment into 8x8 tiles, where each tile is encoded independently from the others. The 8x8 tiling setup is common in 360° video streaming as it provides a reasonable trade-off between flexibility and compression efficiency [45]. Tile compression was performed using Fraunhofer's versatile video encoder (VVenC) [46]. The encoding was performed using four quantization parameters (QP=22, 28, 34, 40), producing four different quality levels. The preset encoding parameter was set to medium in all runs.

We use 40 (out of 60) video sequences to train the viewport prediction model and the remaining 20 videos for evaluating our transmission framework. The evaluation video sequences belong to different content categories including sports, computer-generated (CG), and indoor sceneries. They also vary in their pixel resolution and average encoding bitrates. The specifications of the evaluation videos, along with the resulting tile encoding bitrates, are summarized in Table 2.

Selecting a spatiotemporally diverse set of 360° videos is crucial for providing a reliable performance evaluation as it accounts for the variety of omnidirectional content watched by users and anticipates their corresponding watching behavior in different scenarios.

Figure 6. SI-TI graph of the evaluation 360° videos.

TABLE 2. Summary of the evaluation 360° videos.

Video title	Category	Pixel Resolution	Frame Rate (fps)	Tile average bitrate (Mbps)			
				QP=22	QP=28	QP=34	QP=40
AlpsParagliding	Sports	3840x1920	25	0.655	0.277	0.124	0.063
UcaimaWaterfall	Scenery		30	1.130	0.498	0.197	0.121
DrivingInCity	Scenery		30	0.909	0.210	0.071	0.033
DragonCastleAttatck	CG	3840x2048	24	0.515	0.200	0.085	0.039
YosemiteGliding	Sports		24	0.735	0.287	0.122	0.056
ANewEmpire	CG		30	0.907	0.397	0.176	0.079
GreatWall	Scenery	4096x2048	30	1.192	0.390	0.148	0.064
FootballMatch	Sports		30	0.725	0.174	0.062	0.028
ConcertLive	Indoor		30	0.369	0.130	0.059	0.031
Salon	Indoor		30	0.705	0.207	0.082	0.042
Pagoda	Scenery		30	0.732	0.251	0.097	0.046
Shooting	Sports		30	0.844	0.209	0.068	0.029
PressConference	Indoor		30	0.989	0.285	0.090	0.038
OrchestraOfSpheres	Other		24	0.610	0.181	0.071	0.035
DivingWithJellyfish	Scenery		25	1.612	0.622	0.263	0.123
YeahBoy	Indoor	30	0.868	0.290	0.113	0.055	
BloomingAppleOrchards	Scenery	7680x3840	30	1.573	0.775	0.384	0.207
YourMan	Indoor		30	1.402	0.439	0.160	0.071
AuroraQuartzLake	Scenery		30	1.493	0.517	0.168	0.060
DivingWithSharks	CG		30	1.400	0.614	0.264	0.109

Figure 7. Samples from predicted tile-watching percentages using LSTM from four different 360° videos. Each sample is based on a single user's viewing information during one segment of the following video sequences: (a) YosemiteGliding. (b) DragonCastleAttatck. (c) DrivingInCity. (d) DivingWithJellyfish.

To analyze the diversity of the selected videos through quantitative measurements, we compute the spatial information (SI) and temporal information (TI) metrics [47] of the evaluation video sequences. We illustrate the resulting SI-TI graph in Figure 6. This analysis was performed on the original (uncompressed) video sequences in planar ERP representations. As depicted in the SI-TI graph, the spatial and temporal complexities of the evaluation video sequences span over a wide range of SI-TI values, making them ideal for evaluating our 360° video transmission framework.

B. Viewing prediction - LSTM training

To train and test our model, we utilize the viewing information available in the ODV-VQA dataset [30]. The head movement traces associated with 40 omnidirectional videos, after being divided into ten 1s segments, are used to train the LSTM prediction model. For each video, the

viewing directions of 20 different users are used. The output of the LSTM model is set to predict the tile weights corresponding to an 8x8 tiling setup.

For testing, another 20 video sequences are used. The resulting MSE over the test set is 0.0062, while the MSE calculated for viewed tiles only (tiles with non-zero watching percentages) is 0.0883. Four samples of the resulting tile weight predictions compared to the actual tile-watching percentages are visually depicted in Figure 7. The prediction results show the capability of the adopted LSTM model to accurately identify the watched tiles and estimate their importance during the upcoming segment. The figure also highlights two cases where the viewing areas extend over the 360° video edges and the model could still identify the corresponding tiles successfully. Generally, tiles in the viewport center are predicted with high accuracy, whereas tiles at the viewport edge are more prone to prediction errors.

C. Performance evaluation

We consider the multi-user multi-quality tiled 360° video transmission system depicted in Figure 4. We employ the tile quality selection algorithm proposed in section IV-D to assign the quality levels of each tile. In this subsection, we perform the simulation assuming perfect knowledge of the requested tiles and their viewing percentages. This way, we evaluate our proposed greedy algorithm in isolation from the viewing prediction method, providing the baseline for the simulated tile quality selection algorithms. In the next subsection, we employ LSTM tile viewing prediction to study the effect of tile viewing uncertainty on the delivered viewport qualities.

To evaluate our algorithm, we utilize the twenty 360° video sequences described in the previous subsection, each divided into ten 1s segments, and the HM tracing data of 20 users for each video. To test our method, we simulate the tiled 360° video transmission system in the presence of multiple users (up to eight concurrent users) and assess the system's performance based on the constructed viewport's quality at the users' side, i.e., the received VWS-PSNR metric as defined in equation (2).

We test our proposed method and compare its performance with three other approaches which are all described as follows:

- MCKP-Greedy (proposed): Our proposed method introduced in section IV-D. The deployed greedy algorithm prioritizes tiles with higher potential gains, represented by the increase of the $G_{m,n}$ value over the rise in tile bitrate $b_{m,n}$, and assigns higher quality levels accordingly.
- CFOV-based: The CFOV-based simulated method is similar to our solution, but without accounting for the viewed portion of each tile. Thus, the value $a_{m,n}^u$ is set to 1 for all tiles in the user's viewport. Therefore, maximizing the viewport quality as defined in [48], where FoV tile viewing percentages

are not considered. However, the tile quality mapping in [48] is substituted by $G_{m,n,q}$ to have a fair comparison with our approach.

- OptBR: Many works in the literature such as [39] base their quality optimization of tiled 360° video delivery on maximizing the delivered bitrate, assuming it would result in enhanced quality. We implement OptBR as an approach to assess the validity of this assumption and to compare it to our method which considers 360° VQA metrics. For a fair comparison, we also consider tile viewing percentages in OptBR, in addition to bitrates, and gradually increase the quality of tiles until the bandwidth resources are consumed.
- Same_Q: Similar to [49], this approach assigns the same quality level to all tiles within the user's viewport. It selects the maximum possible quality level resulting in a total bitrate lower than the available bandwidth.

We simulate the system under bandwidth availability values from 9-33 Mbps. The number of concurrent users in the simulation also varied up to eight to study the system scalability. We present the viewport qualities, in terms of VWS-PSNR values, resulting from simulating the four algorithms MCKP-Greedy (proposed), CFOV-based, OptBR, and Same_Q in Figure 8. Our proposed solution yields the best viewport quality compared to the other three methods across all the simulated bandwidth conditions. When the available bandwidth is increased (up to 33 Mbps), all four methods are able to provide decent quality as the bandwidth allows most tiles to be sent at high quality. However, for scarce bandwidth conditions (e.g., BW=9 Mbps), our method provides the best performance by a high margin, especially when compared to the Same_Q method, which restricts the quality level increase, and compared to OptBR, which considers tile bitrates, rather than 360° VQA metrics, in its attempt to maximize the quality.

Figure 8. Performance evaluation of the proposed method. Simulation results are shown as the resulting VWS-PSNR under eight bandwidth scenarios (BW=9-33 Mbps) and for a range of concurrent users varying from 1-8.

Figure 9. Performance evaluation results with LSTM tile-watching percentage prediction, presented for four different videos at *total bandwidth* of 13 Mbps. (a) Center viewing traces for all 20 users. (b) An instance for the corresponding tile-viewing on 8x8 grid in the presence of eight random users. (c) Delivered viewport qualities for the proposed method as a function of the number of concurrent users in the cases of perfect and predicted tile-viewing percentages.

The relatively weak performance of OptBR confirms our discussion in Subsection III-B on the unreliability of bitrate values in reflecting the video corresponding quality. Our method also surpasses CFOV-based in terms of delivered viewports quality, especially for high number of users. This is attributed to the incorporation of tiles watching percentages in the optimization process, where higher qualities are assigned to fully-watched tiles that are common among multiple users. Of all simulated methods, our approach has the best scalability in terms of the number of concurrent users. The performance of CFOV-based, OptBR, and Same_Q deteriorates as the number of users in the system increases. Meanwhile, our proposed method shows high robustness in this regard.

D. Effect of viewing prediction

Since future viewing directions of VR users are not known in advance, viewing prediction models are typically utilized to assist in 360° video streaming. However, prediction inaccuracies and failures can affect the transmission decisions and outcomes, leading to QoE degradation. The degree of prediction error and the resulting QoE degradation depend heavily on the prediction window and the adopted prediction model. Moreover, the users' exploration behavior is subject to the 360° video content. Videos with a single attention point (subject) and static or slow movements produce highly correlated viewing traces among different users, which are likely to be at a slow pace and focus on a common limited area. Such viewing patterns are easy to predict compared to the ones arising from dynamic videos with more detailed scenes and a larger number of subjects. In the context of tiled 360° video streaming, this influences the tile selection process and thus affects the delivered

viewport qualities. To evaluate the effect of viewing prediction on the viewport qualities delivered using our tile quality selection scheme, we employ the LSTM tile-viewing prediction model introduced in section IV. First, we study the effects of tile-viewing prediction on 360° video delivery across videos of different characteristics. Figure 9 illustrates the difference between using the true tile-viewing percentages (ideal case) and the predicted tile-viewing percentages (practical case) from the LSTM network for four 360° videos. The first two videos are in 4K format and have low bitrates compared to the other two 8K videos as detailed in Table 2. Hence, the transmission performance is better in terms of the delivered viewport qualities for the FootballMatch and Salon videos even when the true tile weights are used (VWS-PSNR of 45dB compared to 40-42 dB).

Figure 10. Performance evaluation on true (ideal) and LSTM-predicted tile weights in the presence of eight concurrent users.

However, when the predicted viewing values are used, the margin between the true and prediction-based results is smaller for the FootballMatch compared to the Salon video. This is attributed to the lower and more predictable exploration in the case of the former.

In the case of the 8K 360° video, the dynamic high exploration of the DivingWithJellyfish video yields a significantly larger number of requested tiles than the AuroraQuartzLake video. Therefore, it resulted in higher VWS-PSNR values as the available bandwidth does not allow for sending all viewport tiles at high-quality levels. It should be noted that for all four videos, the gap between the ideal results and the prediction-based results shrinks as the number of concurrent users increases due to the inclusion of predicted tiles from different users. Tiles that are mistakenly excluded for one user due to prediction error, can be considered based on the prediction from another user.

Figure 10 presents the performance evaluation results from the three implemented methods in the case of eight concurrent users averaged across the 20 test dataset videos. The simulation is performed in a range of total bandwidth availability from 9-33 Mbps. For each tile quality selection method, simulation results are provided using the true (ideal) tile weights and using the predicted ones. Our proposed method (MCKP-Greedy) achieves the highest delivered VWS-PSNR. It is also more resilient to prediction errors as indicated by the smaller gap between true and LSTM-based results compared to the other two methods. In the simulated bandwidth range, MCKP-Greedy delivers higher VWS-PSNR values than other methods by 0.67-1.28 dB.

E. Real-life streaming examples

In this part, we present the testing results of two real-world settings that provide insights into the applicability of our method in real-life scenarios. The first part utilizes the widely used streaming protocol, MPEG-DASH, and shows how the information about tiles' spatial positions and available qualities can be embedded in its media presentation description (MPD) files. In the second example, we simulate our method using real-life 5G bandwidth traces and assess its performance under varying bandwidth conditions.

MPEG-DASH streaming of tiled 360° videos: MPEG-DASH [50] is a widely adopted protocol for adaptive video streaming and is used by many video streaming platforms and supported by most browsers and streaming devices. With the proliferation of video applications and streaming techniques, MPEG-DASH implemented the spatial relationship description (SRD) feature in its framework, allowing video content to be divided into spatial regions which then can be streamed independently [51], [52]. This feature is particularly useful for tile-based 360° video streaming as it allows tiles to be fetched independently at their desired qualities. The SRD information is added to the media presentation description (MPD) file which is written in XML and contains a description of the available video content in an MPEG-DASH streaming setup including available video resolutions, segment information, etc. The SRD specifies the relative spatial information of media

assets (i.e., tiles) including their sizes and their horizontal and vertical positions within the whole video.

In this example, we prepare 360° videos for tile-based MPEG-DASH streaming and create the associated MPD files, containing the SRD information, using the MP4Box software [53]. MP4Box provides a set of multimedia packaging functionalities that include SRD-supported DASHing for tiled 360° videos. In Figure 11, we present an example of the resulting MPD files, showing the relevant information for one of the 360° tiles that belong to the FootballMatch video of the used dataset. However, the complete MPD file contains additional information and provides the description of all tiles and quality versions. In this figure, two representations of the same tile are available, a high-quality version (QP=22) at 50.6 Kbps and a low-quality version (QP=40) at 8.6 Kbps. With the SRD information provided in the MPD file, the client can reconstruct the 360° video correctly. By utilizing the SRD feature, our proposed tile-quality selection algorithm can be deployed in any MPEG-DASH streaming system for adapting the tiles' quality levels according to the available bandwidth and transmitting 360° videos efficiently.

5G network scenario: To evaluate our method against real-life bandwidth conditions, we utilize bandwidth traces from a 5G dataset [54]. We use these bandwidth traces to simulate the tile quality selection algorithm proposed in this work and evaluate its performance under varying real-life channel conditions. Figure 12 shows the available bandwidth over time and the corresponding delivered qualities obtained from transmitting 360° videos using our algorithm to eight concurrent users. We present four cases, corresponding to the four videos used in V-D, each under different network conditions. We observe that, for each case, the delivered quality for individual users is similar even in instances of low-bandwidth availability. The low variance of delivered quality among users ensures high fairness and reliability in the system. This is attributed to considering the correlation among users' viewports in our algorithm by incorporating their tile viewing percentages.

```

1 - <Period duration="PT0H0M1.000S">
2 -   <AdaptationSet maxWidth="512" maxHeight="256"
      maxFrameRate="30">
3 -     <SupplementalProperty schemeIdUri="urn:mpeg:dash
      :srd:2014" value="0,0,0,512,256,4096,2048"/>
4 -     <Representation id="1" codecs="hev1.1.6.L63.90"
      width="512" height="256" frameRate="30"
      bandwidth="50648">
5 -       <BaseURL
      >G9FootballMatch_4096x2048_fps30_s0_tile0_
      qp22_dashinit.mp4</BaseURL>
6 -     </Representation>
7 -     <Representation id="2" codecs="hev1.1.6.L63.90"
      width="512" height="256" frameRate="30"
      bandwidth="8608">
8 -       <BaseURL>G9FootballMatch_4096x2048_fps30_s0_tile0_qp40
      _dashinit.mp4</BaseURL>
9 -     </Representation>
10 -   </AdaptationSet>
11 -   <!-- Additional AdaptationSets for remaining tiles
      would follow the same pattern -->
12 </Period>

```

Figure 11. Example of an MPEG-DASH MPD with SRD information for one tile available in two quality representations.

Figure 12. Evaluation of the proposed tile quality selection method for four different videos in the presence of eight users using 5G bandwidth traces. (a) available bandwidth in the 5G network over time. (b) Delivered video quality for all eight users.

For the low-bitrate videos (FootballMatch and Salon), the delivered viewport quality is high and relatively stable, with small quality drops in low-bandwidth events. Whereas the high-bitrate videos experience higher quality changes, as they need higher bandwidth to be delivered at high quality.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this work, we investigated the tile quality selection problem in multi-user tiled 360° video transmission and proposed an optimized solution to maximize the users' viewport quality based on 360° VQA metrics. By aggregating tile weights across multiple users' viewports, our algorithm aligns with the highly correlated viewing patterns observed among different users. This approach ensured high scalability and robustness against increasing the number of concurrent users. Additionally, by prioritizing viewport central tiles over partially-viewed edge tiles, our method demonstrated high resilience to viewing prediction errors which tend to be more severe for viewport edge tiles. We have conducted extensive simulations and evaluated our approach using a diverse 360° video viewing dataset. The evaluation showed that our method enhances the quality of delivered viewports by incorporating tiles viewing ratios into its decision-making criteria, ensuring superior viewport quality compared to other methods. In the case of eight concurrent users, a 0.67-1.28 dB improvement in the delivered VWS-PSNR was achieved when simulated in practical scenarios.

By demonstrating the necessity of considering 360° VQA metrics and users' viewing patterns in optimizing multi-user tiled 360° video streaming, we pave the way for new research opportunities in this direction. For instance, the viewport quality definition formulated in this work should be integrated into a more general QoE model that considers additional aspects of 360° video transmission, such as responsiveness and quality fluctuations, to develop a more comprehensive streaming framework. Moreover, the quality modeling and insights gained in this study can be applied to optimize other network scenarios that may demand different optimization techniques.

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